

Synthesis, characterization, thermal behavior and biological studies of VO^{IV} and MoO₂^{VI} complexes of hydrazone ligand

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Abstract : New biologically active complexes of VO^{IV} and MoO₂^{VI} with 2-hydroxyacetophenone pyrazine-2-carbohydrazone (H₂L) ligand derived from the condensation of 2-hydroxyacetophenone with pyrazine-2-carbohydrazide have been synthesized. Both the complexes and the ligand have been characterized by various physical measurements such as elemental analyses and spectroscopic techniques. The elemental analysis shows 1 : 1 metal to ligand stoichiometry for both the complexes. The molar conductance measurements of the complexes in DMF suggest their nonelectrolytic nature. The ligand work as tridentate *ONO*, being coordinated through the phenolic oxygen, azomethine nitrogen and enolic oxygen atoms. MoO₂^{VI} complex was found to have six-coordinate octahedral geometry while the VO^{IV} complex was five coordinate square pyramidal nature. Thermal behavior of the complexes was studied, the complexes were found to be quite stable and their thermal decomposition was generally via partially loss of the organic moiety and ended with respective metal oxide as a final product. ESR spectrum of the VO^{IV} complex in polycrystalline state at room (300 K) was recorded and its salient features are reported. Antimicrobial studies were also conducted to assess the growth inhibiting potential of the free Schiff base ligand and its complexes against some bacteria and fungi.

Keywords : Hydrazone ligand, metal complexes, spectral analysis, TGA, antimicrobial activity.

Introduction

Hydrazones are of interest, because of their versatility in coordinating to metals, flexibility in assuming different confirmations, pharmacological activity and their use in analytical methods. They can coordinate either in the neutral or in anionic form. Furthermore, the possibility of tautomerism make their study extremely interesting¹⁻⁹. Many hydrazone complexes reported in the literature have been studied electrochemically, using various electrodes and solvents, with a view to understand the mechanism of their biological activities. The pyrazonic acid hydrazone derivatives containing heterocyclic moiety were found to exhibit remarkable biological and anti-tubercular activity. Therefore, it was thought of interest, to prepare the hydrazone of pyrazine-2-carbohydrazide containing a heterocyclic moiety and obtaining information about the chemical and structural properties of the metal complexes, especially with regard to the stereochemistry and effects of coordination on the conformation of the coordinatively flexible hydrazone, we have undertaken the study of VO^{IV} and MoO₂^{VI} complexes of 2-hydroxyacetophenone

pyrazine-2-carbohydrazone (H₂L). Here we report the synthesis, characterization and thermal behavior of VO^{IV} and MoO₂^{VI} complexes of hydrazone (H₂L) derived from the condensation of pyrazine-2-carbohydrazide and 2-hydroxyacetophenone. The biological activity of the ligand and both complexes against bacterial species *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, *S. aureus*, *B. subtilis*, *E. faecalis* and *S. pyogenes* and fungi *C. albicans*, *A. niger* and *A. clavatus* have also been studied.

Results and discussion

The elemental analyses suggest 1 : 1 (metal to ligand) stoichiometry for both the complexes. The analytical data along with some physical properties of the complexes are summarized in Table 1. Both the complexes are colored solid and insoluble in common organic solvents but found soluble in DMF and DMSO respectively. The molar conductance values of the complexes in DMF are lies in the range 12.5–16.3 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ indicating their non-electrolytic nature.

IR spectra :

In order to study the binding mode of the ligand to

metal in the complexes, the IR spectrum of the free ligand was compared with the spectra of those complexes and the coordination sites were ascertained on the basis of shifts in the wavenumber of various groups. The ligand spectrum shows a broad band centered around at 3346 cm^{-1} due to hydrogen bonded phenolic OH. Absence of this band in spectra of both the complexes indicates that the proton gets dissociated after complexation¹⁰. This is further supported by the upward shifting of phenolic C–O stretching vibrations from 1301 cm^{-1} to $1309\text{--}1330\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in both the complexes, indicates the coordination of phenolic oxygen to the metal ion¹¹. The ligand exhibits bands at 3182 cm^{-1} and 1691 cm^{-1} due to $\nu(\text{N-H})$ and $\nu(\text{C=O})$ stretching respectively and are disappeared completely in the spectra of both complexes indicating enolization followed by deprotonation prior to coordination of the ligand to the metal ion¹². This has been further confirmed by the appearance of new enolic band in the region $1227\text{--}1238\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to $\nu(\text{C-O})$ in the spectra of complexes. The enolization is favored by the stabilization of the anion by the conjugation with the $>\text{C}=\text{N}-\text{N}=\text{C}<$ group¹³. The strong azomethine band of free ligand was observed at 1630 cm^{-1} and in the spectra of complexes, this band get shifted to lower wavenumber ($1597\text{--}1610\text{ cm}^{-1}$), indicating that nitrogen of azomethine group undergoes coordination with metal ion¹⁴. The ligand spectrum shows band at 977 cm^{-1} due to $\nu(\text{N-N})$ stretching which further shifted to higher wavenumber by $4\text{--}27\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of complexes also supports the involvement of the azomethine nitrogen atom in the coordination with the metal ion¹⁵. The oxovanadium(IV) complex shows a strong band at 972 cm^{-1} due to $\nu(\text{V=O})$ modes¹⁶. Dioxomolybdenum(VI) complex exhibits bands at 858 and 914 cm^{-1} due to symmetric and asymmetric stretching frequency of *cis*- MoO_2 . Using McGlynn and Jones method^{17,18}, the $F_{\text{Mo-O}}$ and $R_{\text{Mo-O}}$ are calculated and are found to be $6.90\text{ mdynes \AA}^{-1}$ and 1.74 \AA , respectively. The broad band at $3398\text{--}3399$, $1560\text{--}1568$ and $852\text{--}877\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of the complexes are due to $\nu(\text{OH})$, $\delta\gamma(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ and $\delta\omega(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ vibrations for the coordinated water molecules¹⁹. The non-ligand bands occurring in the range $501\text{--}505$ and $438\text{--}477\text{ cm}^{-1}$ have been assigned to $\nu(\text{M-O})$ and $\nu(\text{M-N})$ respectively²⁰. Therefore, the infrared data of the ligand and its metal complexes indicate coordination of the ligand through the phenolic oxygen and azomethine nitrogen and enolic oxygen atom.

Electronic spectra and magnetic moments :

The VO^{IV} complex exhibits three bands at 13477 , 18832 and 28011 cm^{-1} due to ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2E$, ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_1$ and ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2A_1$, transitions, respectively towards square pyramidal geometry around VO^{IV} ion²¹. The magnetic moment obtained for VO^{IV} complex at room temperature is found to be 1.72 B.M. which is also close to the spin only value for one unpaired electron. The MoO_2^{VI} complex did not show any d-d transitions and found to be diamagnetic as expected for its electronic configuration and likely to be an octahedral geometry around the metal ion²².

ESR :

The ESR spectrum of VO^{IV} complex has been recorded in polycrystalline state at room temperature. The ESR spectrum of the VO^{IV} complex exhibits one band at $g = \sim 1.98$ without any hyperfine structure indicating square pyramidal geometry around VO^{IV} ion which is also supported by electronic and magnetic moment data. The g value ~ 1.98 is invariably lower than the free electron value ($g_e = 2.0023$).

${}^1\text{H}$ NMR spectra :

Coordination of the ligand in the MoO_2^{VI} complex is further confirmed by its ${}^1\text{H}$ NMR spectrum of the complex. The ${}^1\text{H}$ NMR spectrum of the ligand shows signals at 12.99 ppm -OH (1H, s) and 11.44 ppm -NH (1H, s). The ${}^1\text{H}$ NMR spectrum of the MoO_2^{VI} complex shows absence of phenolic -OH, confirming involvement of the -OH proton in complexation via deprotonation. The signal for NH proton gets disappeared which supports the coordination through enolic form of ligand to the MoO_2^{VI} ion. ${}^1\text{H}$ NMR of $[\text{Mo}_2(\text{L})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ complex (DMSO- d_6 , 400 MHz) : δ 9.36 (1H, s, C3-H), 8.80 (2H, m, C5-H and C6-1H), 7.96 (1H, dd, C11-H), 7.52 (1H, m, C9-H), 7.10 (1H, dd, C8-H), 6.96 (1H, dd, C10), 2.93 (3H, s, CH_3). There are no appreciable changes in other signals of the MoO_2^{VI} complex.

Mass spectra :

Mass spectrum of the ligand shows the molecular ion peak at $m/z = 257.2$, which correspond to the molecular mass of the ligand and its purity. The mass spectra of the VO^{IV} and MoO_2^{VI} complexes show a molecular ion peak (M^+) at $m/z = 339.1$ and 401.9 respectively, indicative of their monomeric nature.

Powder XRD :

X-Ray powder pattern of VO^{IV} complex has been recorded as a representative compound. The well defined Bragg's peaks at specific 2θ angles show high crystallinity of the complex. X-Ray crystal system has been worked out by trial and error method for finding the best fit between observed and calculated values. The unit cell parameters of the complex are as follows; [VO(L)(H₂O)] : system = monoclinic, *a* = 5.8846 Å, *b* = 11.7702 Å, *c* = 7.5759 Å, β = 97.141°, *V* = 520.66 Å³. The average crystallite size of the VO^{IV} complex was calculated from Scherer's formula^{23,24}. Using the full width at half maximum intensity of the pattern, the average size of the crystal is around 38 nm, indicating that the complex is in nanocrystalline phase.

SEM :

The SEM micrographs of the VO^{IV} and MoO₂^{VI} complexes (Figs. 1 and 2) show that the VO^{IV} complex has agglomerated cluster, while MoO₂^{VI} complex exhibits mono disperse granular like structure. The smaller average crystallite size observed from XRD also suggests that the particles are agglomerated in nature.

Fig. 1. SEM pattern of [VO(L)(H₂O)] complex.

Fig. 2. SEM pattern of [MoO₂(L)(H₂O)] complex.

Thermal analysis :

Thermal decomposition studies of complexes have been carried out as to corroborate the information obtained from the IR spectral studies to know the presence of water molecules in these complexes as well as to know their decomposition pattern. The thermogravimetric analyses of compounds were carried out in the temperature range from ambient to 750 °C at a heating rate of 10 °C min⁻¹. The TGA results reveal that ligand (H₂L) decompose in a single stage, whereas VO^{IV} and MoO₂^{VI} complexes decomposed in two stages. The weight loss in first stage 90–190 °C is due the loss of coordinated water molecules from the complexes^{25,26}. After the loss of coordinated water, both the complexes show rapid degradation up to 750 °C. This may be due to the decomposition of organic part of the complex, indicated by the rapid fall in the percentage mass loss. A horizontal plateau on the TG curves for both the complexes indicates the decomposition of the organic part of the chelate in the last stage leaving residues of metallic oxide at the higher temperature range. The decomposition temperatures of the complexes are higher than that of the ligand, indicates that the thermal stability of the complexes are increased due to the ligand coordinating with metal ions to form stable ring.

Antimicrobial activity :

The antimicrobial activity of ligand (H₂L) and its metal complexes were tested against the bacterial stains *S. aureus* MTCC 96, *S. pyogenes* MTCC 442, *B. subtilis* MTCC 8979, *E. coli* MTCC 443, *P. aeruginosa* MTCC 424 and *E. faecalis* MTCC 439 and fungal stains *A. niger* MTCC 282, *A. clavatus* MTCC 1323, *C. albicans* MTCC 227. The results of inhibition are compared with standard antibacterial drug ciprofloxacin and antifungal drug clotrimazole. The antimicrobial results are given in Table 2. All the investigated compounds showed a remarkable biological activity against bacteria and fungi. The obtained results reflect that; VO^{IV} and MoO₂^{VI} complexes show moderate activity against all bacterial and fungal stains. Generally, all of the metal complexes show higher antimicrobial properties compared to the free ligand (H₂L). Coordination reduces the polarity²⁷ of the metal ion, mainly because of the partial sharing of its positive charge with the donor groups within the chelate ring system formed during coordination. This process, in turn, increases the lipophilic nature of the central metal atom, which favors

Table 1. Physico-chemical data of the metal complexes

Compound	Formula	Formula weight	Colour	Elemental analysis (%) :				Molar conductance ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)
				Found (Calcd.)				
				C	H	N	M	
[VO(L)(H ₂ O)]	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₄ V	340.12	Chartreuse	46.03 (46.17)	3.21 (3.63)	16.86 (16.29)	15.24 (15.00)	16.3
[MoO ₂ (L)(H ₂ O)]	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₅ Mo	400.67	Mustard	40.97 (40.06)	3.58 (3.09)	14.18 (14.19)	24.32 (24.06)	12.5

Table 2. Antimicrobial activity of the H₂L ligand and its metal complexes

Compound	Minimum inhibitory concentration ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)								
	<i>E. coli</i> (MTCC 443)	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> (MTCC 424)	<i>S. aureus</i> (MTCC 96)	<i>B. subtilis</i> (MTCC 8979)	<i>E. faecalis</i> (MTCC 439)	<i>S. pyogenes</i> (MTCC 442)	<i>C. albican</i> (MTCC 227)	<i>A. niger</i> (MTCC 282)	<i>A. clavatus</i> (MTCC 1323)
H ₂ L	12	12	13	9	9	8	11	10	10
[VO(L)(H ₂ O)]	13	13	14	12	11	10	12	12	11
[MoO ₂ (L)(H ₂ O)]	14	13	14	10	11	11	12	11	11
Ciprofloxacin ^a	13	14	14	14	15	12	–	–	–
Clotrimazole ^a	–	–	–	–	–	–	13	9	12

^aStandard drug.

its permeation more efficiently through the lipid layer of the microorganism²⁸, thus destroying them more aggressively. Some important factors, such as the nature of the metal ion, nature of the ligand, coordinating sites, geometry of the complex, concentration, hydrophilicity, lipophilicity and presence of co-ligands, have considerable influence on the antibacterial activity. From the antimicrobial study, it is found that, the tested compounds possess better antimicrobial activities and also comparable to standards used.

Conclusions

A heterocyclic hydrazone ligand was prepared by condensation of 2-hydroxyacetophenone with pyrazine-2-carbohydrazide. This new ligand formed a VO^{IV} and MoO₂^{VI} metal complexes and their spectral properties were studied. Spectral data suggested that the ligand coordinated to the metal ion in a tridentate fashion. An octahedral geometry was proposed to MoO₂^{VI} complex while square pyramidal geometry to VO^{IV}. Powder XRD study showed that the high crystallinity of the complex as compare to the ligand. The biological activity of both the metal complexes are comparable with the standard used and have shown comparatively good activity against bacteria and fungi. The results of antimicrobial activity show that the metal complexes exhibit antimicrobial properties

and it is important to note that they show enhanced inhibitory activity compared to the parent ligand under identical experimental conditions.

Experimental

Materials and physical measurements :

All chemicals used were of either A.R. or chemically pure grade. The solvents obtained from commercial sources were dried using standard methods²⁹ as and when required. All the metal salts were obtained from SD fine chemicals and were used as received.

The IR spectra were recorded as KBr pellets using a Shimadzu 8201 spectrophotometer in the range 400–4000 cm⁻¹. Elemental analyses were carried out on a Carlo Erba 1108 elemental analyzer. ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker Advance II, 400 MHz, NMR spectrophotometer in DMSO-*d*₆ with TMS as an internal standard. Magnetic measurements were carried out by the Sherwood magnetic susceptibility balance MK1 at room temperature. The solid-state reflectance spectra of the complexes were recorded in the 200–1000 nm range (as MgO) disc on a Cary 60 UV-Vis spectrophotometer. The X-band ESR spectrum of VO^{IV} complex was recorded on Varian E-112 spectrophotometer using TCNE (tetracyanoethylene) as the *g*-marker. Thermogravimetric analyses were performed on a Perkin-Elmer, Diamond

TG thermal analyzer in the temperature range 40–750 °C with a heating rate of 10 °C min⁻¹. Metal contents of the complexes were analyzed gravimetrically after decomposing the organic matter with a mixture of HClO₄, H₂SO₄ and HNO₃ (1 : 1.5 : 2.5) and then igniting to metal oxide. X-Ray diffraction patterns were obtained with a Bruker AXS, D8 Advance equipped with Si(Li) PDS. Mass spectra were recorded on a Waters, Q-TOF micromass (LC-MS) spectrometer. The surface morphology was observed using a JEOL Model JSM-6390LV scanning electron microscope. The molar conductance was recorded using 10⁻³ molar solutions in DMSO with an Elico conductivity bridge and dip type cell calibrated with KCl solution.

Synthesis :

Synthesis of the ligand (H₂L) :

Ethanol solution of pyrazine-2-carbohydrazide (1 g, 0.0072 mmol) was added dropwise to the magnetically stirred ethanol solution (10 ml) of 2-hydroxyacetophenone (0.9862 g, 0.0072 mmol) and reaction mixture was refluxed for 3 h on water bath. The progress of reaction was monitored by TLC. The resulting Schiff base that separated out on cooling the reaction mixture was filtered, washed with ethanol and recrystallized with DMF. Yield : 63%. Microanalytical data for C₁₃H₁₂N₄O₂. Anal. Calcd. : C, 60.93; H, 4.72; N, 21.86. Found : C, 61.12; H, 4.70; N, 21.83%; IR (KBr disc, cm⁻¹) : 3346 (OH), 3102 (NH), 1691 ν(C=O), 1630 ν(C=N), 1301 (C-O); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 400 MHz) : δ 12.99 (1H, s, OH), 11.44 (1H, s, NH), 9.31 (1H, s, C3-H), 8.94 (1H, d, *J* 2.4 Hz, C5-H), 8.77 (1H, d, *J* 2.4 Hz, C6-H), 7.71 (1H, dd, *J* 1.4 and 6.7 Hz, C11-H), 7.59 (1H, dd, *J* 1.4 and 6.7 Hz, C8-H), 7.28 (2H, m, C10-H), 2.54 (3H, s, CH₃); ¹³C NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 100 MHz) : 167.80 (C=N), 158.78 (C=O), 159.74 (C12), 147.85 (C6), 144.04 (C2), 143.85 (C3), 143.12 (C5), 132.48 (C10), 131.39 (C8), 128.34 (C9), 118.71 (C7), 117.29 (C11), 14.66 (CH₃). Mass spectrum (ESI) [M]⁺ = 257.2.

Synthesis of the VO^{IV} and MoO₂^{VI} complexes of ligand (H₂L) :

Equimolar quantities (0.01 mol) of ligand and appropriate metal salt were dissolved separately in DMF (25 ml) and hot ethanol respectively. Both the solutions were filtered and mixed them in hot condition under continuous stirring. The resulting reaction mixture was refluxed for

6–8 h on an oil bath. On cooling to room temperature, the colored complex precipitated out was filtered, washed with DMF, methanol and petroleum ether and finally dried under vacuum at room temperature. Yield : 65–68%.

Antimicrobial activity :

The bacterial strains, *E. coli* MTCC 443, *P. aeruginosa* MTCC 424, *S. aureus* MTCC 96, *B. subtilis* MTCC 8979, *E. faecalis* MTCC 439 and *S. pyogenes* MTCC 442 and fungal strains, *C. albicans* MTCC 227, *A. niger* MTCC 282 and *A. clavatus* MTCC 1323 were used in the study. The solutions of ciprofloxacin (antibacterial drug) and clotrimazole (antifungal drug) were used as standard. The disc agar diffusion method³⁰ was employed for the determination of antimicrobial activities. MICs (minimum inhibitory concentration) of the compounds against test organisms were determined by the broth micro dilution method. All the tests were performed in duplicate and repeated twice. Modal values were selected.

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